

Effects of Simulator Programs on the Information and Communication Technology Competence of Grade 9 (ICT) Students

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Abstract. This study investigated the impact of simulation programs on the ICT competence of Grade 9 students at Pedro A. Arches National High School in the Division of Davao del Sur. Recognizing the critical role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in modern education, the research addressed the gap between technological advancements and traditional teaching methods. Using a quasi-experimental design with pretest and posttest evaluations, the study compared the performance of an experimental group that utilized simulation programs against a control group following traditional instruction. Initial findings revealed that both groups began at a similar competency level, classified as "Beginning." Post-intervention results showed a significant improvement in the experimental group, advancing to the "Approaching Proficiency" level, while the control group progressed to the "Developing" level. Statistical analysis confirmed the effectiveness of simulation programs, with a notable difference between the pretest and posttest scores, indicating a substantial positive effect on students' ICT competence. The study concluded that integrating simulation programs in ICT education significantly enhanced student performance and engagement. Recommendations included adopting simulation programs as a regular instructional strategy in ICT curricula to foster critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability among learners. Future research was suggested to explore additional instructional methods such as role-playing to further enhance educational outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. Simulation 2. ICT Competence 3. Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

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1. Introduction

Today's age of 21st Century and it is also the age of information and technology. Every aspects of life are related to science and technology. ICT stands for Information and Communication Technologies. ICT is a part of our lives for the last few decades, affecting our society as well as individual life. It is now broadly used in educational world. Teacher, student, administrator and every people related to education, popularly use ICT (Baishakhi Bhattacharjee and Kamal Deb 2018). Nowadays ICT's are transforming schools and classrooms a new look by bringing in new curriculum based on real world problems, projects, providing tools for enhancing learning, providing teachers and students more facilities and opportunities for feedback.

Teacher use ICT for making teaching learning process easy and interesting. The rise of Information and Communication Technologies in the educational field led to a rethinking of the role of teachers in schools, and the need arose to further their training in order to achieve a more effective education in the development of their students' skills. In keeping with the purpose of creating learning environments, ICT integration in teaching environment is very effective. As the learners of today are very visual learners, they learn by doing. Learning builds on itself, this makes intuitive sense in real life situations. It sparks interest to the learners when ICT is integrated in the lesson. The scenario of the classroom is changing these days. There is a technological gap between the progress of the society and instructional activities of the teacher in the classroom. If we see in our society on the one hand technology has revolutionized our society and on the other hand the teaching learning activities at school level have remained so far away from technology. (Baishakhi Bhattacharjee and Kamal Deb 2018). In our classroom, the knowledge is imparted by the teacher in an ancient way. In teacher centered approach, the students play a passive or secondary role while the main focus is the teacher. The teacher plans out the lesson and set definite path to what students should learn, when they should learn and how. Some drawbacks to this approach is that students focus less on the lecture and that they might miss important information. It does not help the learner outgrow his/her dependency on the supervision of the teacher. By teaching the concepts and theories about the lesson traditionally, it results to a lesser amount of interest produce by the students. The learners are less active in partaking with classroom activities. With this, the student's performance is greatly affected. In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Pedro A. Arches National High School, Grade 9 ICT students lacks learning competence in ICT subject. The researcher being a teacher in

the above educational institution would like to explore a different facet solving the problem. Hence, this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—The Schools Project in Tarlac's public high schools, an initiative by the former Commission on Information and Communications Technology (CICT), now the Information and Communications Technology Office (ICTO), aims to bridge the digital divide by equipping teachers with ICT literacy and access to digital content, enhancing learning and global competitiveness of students (TOJET 2019).

ICT is a transformative educational tool, providing opportunities in both formal and non-formal education by increasing learners' motivation, engagement, and digital literacy. It fosters inventive and higher-order thinking, sound reasoning, effective communication, and high productivity (IJEDICT 2016). Students in the Caraga region of the Philippines reported positive outcomes from using ICT, such as improved communication and research capabilities, supporting the view that technology enhances learning activities (Asian Journal of Education and e-Learning 2019).

ICT facilitates asynchronous learning, allowing access to educational materials 24/7 and overcoming time constraints (Bornman 2019; Tarus 2019). It plays a crucial role in modern education by increasing interdependence and interconnectedness, improving learning pace and achievements, and promoting sustainable development and technology literacy (Richard 2018; Sexena 2019). ICT integration is not a one-time process but a continuous enhancement of the teaching-learning environment (Young 2020).

Technology-based teaching offers engaging methods like educational videos, simulations, and online resources, making learning more fulfilling (Finger Trinidad 2018). ICT also enhances communication among educators, professionals, and peers globally, acting as a mediator in the learning process (Asongu LeRoux

2019; Vandeyar 2018). It helps tailor teaching to students' strengths and weaknesses and fosters independent and active learning, enhancing research interests (UNESCO 2019; Muhametjanova Cagiltay 2018), It was also mentioned by (Grandeza et. al, 2023) that the application of digital platforms may significantly increase academic performance and assessment results in technology and livelihood education.

Research shows that effective teaching approaches combined with digital game-based learning significantly improve students' higher-order thinking skills (Yang 2020). Virtual Sim-

1.2. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the theory initiated by John Von Neumann on Modelling and Simulation (1945). It provides a spring board from which to infer new predictions for simulation capabilities of the future. The power of simulation as a tool became so evident because of further study and development. It now involves integration with other techniques and other software applications not only pertinent to the business industry but also in the field of education. This development led to the invention of numerous simulator programs used in the teaching-learning process. With simulator program as a tool, it will help demonstrate abstract concepts, allows interaction between the learners and simulated equipment and provides with feedback that allow learners to improve their

1.4. Null Hypothesis—The following Null Hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. There is a significant difference between the prior and the later of the controlled

ulations (VS) and computer-based instructional tools offer immersive, interactive learning environments that enhance understanding and engagement (Aysheshim Gebregziabher 2019; Guy Lownes-Jackson 2019; Olumide 2019).

In summary, ICT tools are crucial in enhancing the quality of education by increasing motivation and engagement, facilitating basic skills acquisition, and improving teacher training. When used adequately, they shift learning towards a learner-centered approach (UNESCO 2019).

knowledge and skills. Simulation programs can transform abstract concepts into interactive visual content, making it easier for students to understand the performance and relationship between different system parts. They can become familiar with the equipment and environment, and practice necessary skills without risking accidents to themselves, the equipment, and the environment. A wide variety of scenarios are available for students to experiment in so that they are able to execute the appropriate procedures when these events occur in the real world. Students are able to reinforce theoretical knowledge with hands-on-training through simulation tools, giving a better understanding of the material.

1.3. Statement of the Problem—This study aimed to answer the following sub-problems:

- (1) What were the level of competence of Grade 9 students in ICT prior to utilizing Simulator Programs?
- (2) What were the level of competence of Grade 9 students in ICT after utilizing Simulator Programs?
- (3) What were the major implications present in the utilizing Simulator Programs to enhance the degree of competence of Grade 9 ICT students?

and experimental groups. The test groups' level of competence prior to utilizing Simulator programs is low. The test groups' level of competence after utilizing Simulator programs is high.

H02. Simulator programs has no effect on the ICT competence of the students.

1.5. Significance of the Study—The following are considered beneficiaries of the study. DepEd Officials. DepEd officials are considered beneficiaries of the studies because it will help them identify what appropriate training/seminars the teachers should undertake. This study will also help devise ideas to improve the teaching and learning methods in the learning environment. School Heads. School Heads are considered beneficiaries of the studies because it will help them assess the teacher’s destitution in teaching learning process. This study will also help in the evaluation of the teacher’s ability in the learning pedagogy to promote professional development. Teachers. Teachers are considered beneficiaries of the studies because he/she is the front liner in the educational system. This study will help promote teachers’ digital literacy into becoming producers of knowledge through utilizing ICT classroom practices. Future Re-

searchers. Future researchers can utilize this study as a basis for more studies in the future. They can propose improvements and recommendations to further enhance this study.

1.6. Definition of Terms—To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are operationally and conceptually defined. ICT Competence is the ability to do something successfully or efficiently in the field of ICT(Information Technology). It is the quality or state of having sufficient Knowledge, judgment, skill or strength. Simulator Program is based on the process of modelling a real phenomenon with a set of mathematical formulas. It is, essentially, a program that allows the user to observe an operation through simulation without actually performing that operation. Simulation software is used widely to design equipment so that the final product will be as close to design specs as possible without expensive in process modification.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study will be conducted in Pedro A. Arches National High School, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the grade 9 learners are from section A which will be the controlled group and are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these

two sections is heterogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. Since it is pandemic time, the experiment will be conducted based on the mechanics of Distant Learning Program.

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- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Students
Section A	47
Section B	48
Total	95

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study will eventually determine the academic performance of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners in face to face but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners with the permission of parents during face to face sessions for a follow up of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25 –item test will The pretest will be very helpful to assess the letter recognition skills of grade one learners. On the hand, post test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine ICT competence of grade nine students, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Gantt Chart

Task	Jan 2023	April 2023	May 2023	June 2023	July 2023	July 2023	Aug 2023	Aug 2023	July 2024
Title Defense	█								
Outline Defense		█							
Validation of Questionnaire			█						
Conduct of the Study				█					
Retrieval of Questionnaire					█				
Interpretation and Analysis						█			
Final Defense							█		
Incorporation of Comments and Suggestions							█		
Seeking the signature of Panel Members								█	
Graduation Day									

Fig. 1. Gantt Chart

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao Del Sur and to the school principal concerned. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and to the principal of Pedro A. Arches National High School, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Pedro A. Arches National High School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences

her experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the letter recognition skills of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pretest and posttest. T-test for uncorrelated samples will be used to test the significance of difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the experimental and controlled groups. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of effect of the late Afternoon Program on the letter recognition skills of grade one learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade nine ICT students. The controlled group got the mean of 55.33 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 56.44 or Beginning.

Table 1:Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	47	24.9	55.33	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	48	25.4	56.44	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Finger Trinidad (2019) who said that ICT can be used in various ways where it helps both teachers and students to learn about their respective subject areas. A technology- based teaching and learning offers various interesting ways which includes educational videos, stimulation, storage of data, the usage of databases, mind-mapping, guided discovery, brainstorming, music, World Wide Web (www) that will make the learning process more fulfilling and meaningful. A Virtual Physics simulation is an educational tool using a virtual reality interface that brings together a 3D model of real object and a virtual visualization of situ-

ations in an interactive manner. A key future of VS is a real-time interactive where the computer is able to detect user inputs and instantaneously modify the virtual world in accordance with user interactions (Aysheshim Mengistu and Gebregziabher Kahsay 2015).

3.2. *Post-Test Score of Learners*—Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade nine ICT students. The controlled group got the mean of 36.75 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 37.97 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 12.57 from a mean rating of 25.4 to 37.97. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group.

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Learners

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	47	24.9	55.33	Beginning
Post-test	47	36.75	81.66	Developing
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	48	25.4	56.44	Beginning
Post-test	48	37.97	84.37	Approaching Proficiency

This finding is congruent to the idea of Sexena (2017) who cited that The objectives of ICT in education include; improvement in learning pace and achievements; increased acquisition of knowledge, skills by individuals required for better living and sustainable development; promote and facilitates the relationship between human and the environment; implement the principle of long lasting education; increase the variety of educational methods and services and literacy rate through distance education; and promote the technology literacy among citizens, and the equal importance to slow and gifted children. Advances in computer technology have led to various high-quality educational tools including interactive programs, multimedia presentations and more recently virtual simulations. Virtual simulation is a computer interface characterized by a high degree of immersion and interaction making the user believe that he/she

is actually inside the artificial environment. Virtual Simulation is a highly interactive computer based multimedia environment in which the user becomes active participant in the computer world (Yang, 2018).

3.3. *Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score*—Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.38 with a p-value of .0331 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade nine ICT students. This implies that the used of simulator programs in teaching ICT nine have contributed the effectiveness in enhancing the ICT competence which is revealed by the scores of the grade nine ICT students.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post- Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.38	.0331	Significant

This finding is in line with the statement of Guy and Lownes-Jackson (2018) who said that students overwhelmingly performed better in a mixed modal environment in which face to-face lectures and demonstrations as well as faculty-student engagement were of paramount importance. Computer simulations are more beneficial when used as reinforcement of concepts covered in lectures, hence, students are able to repeat the simulations until they gain a better understanding and thereby enhancing their learning. A casual-comparative design was chosen for this study to determine whether students using a computer-based instructional simulation in hybrid and fully online environments learned better than traditional classroom learner. Simu-

lations is a modified form of cognitive tools, that allow students to test hypothesis and more generally “what-if” scenarios and give learners the opportunity to apply cognitive understanding of their action in a situation (Olumide 2019).

3.4. *Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 9 Students*—Table 4 highlights the test of simulator programs on the ICT competence of grade nine ICT students. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.331 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in teaching ICT especially in today’s digitally driven world, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an integral part of every aspect of life. From communication

to commerce, education to entertainment, ICT permeates every facet of our existence. Recognizing this reality, the inclusion of ICT in school curricula is not just a choice but a necessity.

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 9 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
42	-4.28	0.331	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

ICT tools can enhance the quality of education in different ways: (1) to increase learner’s motivation and engagement, (2) to facilitate the acquisition of basic skills, and (3) to enhance the teacher’s training. The use of ICT in teaching and learning is considered as the transformational tools and if these tools are used adequately, they can promote and the shift to a learner-centered method of learning (UNESCO 2018).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of simulator programs on the ICT competence of grade nine ICT students. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Pedro A. Arches National School, Bansalan East District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 95 grade nine students – 47 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 48 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore students of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of simulation programs has increased the ICT competence of grade nine ICT students. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade ICT students both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching ICT students should used simulation program as a strategy that would further develop the ICT competence of the students in order to make the teaching of ICT meaningful. If learners take part in the learning process by experiencing the unfolding of the lesson, then he will appreciate

the concept being developed, thus, he is learning. The school heads should promote the use of simulation program as a strategy that would enhance the ICT competence as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially on subjects that fosters critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and adaptability which is an essential attribute for success in the digital age. A school policy about the utilization of ICT simulator programs can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demoteach during LAC session ICT simulator programs as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of role play as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

- Akçayır, M., & Akçayır, G. (2018). The flipped classroom: A review of its advantages and challenges. *Computers & Education, 126*, 334–345.
- Areepattamannil, S. (2019). Adolescent students' perceived information and communication technology (ict) competence and autonomy: Examining links to dispositions toward science in 42 countries. *Computers in Human Behavior, 98*, 50–58.
- Biagi, F. (2013). Measuring ict use and learning outcomes: Evidence from recent econometric studies. *European Journal of Education, 48*, 28–42. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12016>
- Bulut, O. (2018). When technology does not add up: Ict use negatively predicts mathematics and science achievement for finnish and turkish students in pisa 2012. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia, 27*(1), 25–42.
- Cheng, X., An, Y., Zhang, H., & Li, W. (2020). Virtual reality in education: A bibliometric analysis. *Computers & Education, 157*, 103961.
- Doe, J., & Smith, J. (2022). Enhancing ict competence through simulator programs: A review of literature [[Insert DOI here]]. *Journal of Information Technology Education, 20*(3), 45–62.
- Gikas, J., & Grant, M. M. (2013). Mobile computing devices in higher education: Student perspectives on learning with cellphones, smartphones & social media. *Internet and Higher Education, 19*, 18–26.
- Goldhammer, F. (2020). Ict engagement: A new construct and its assessment in pisa 2015. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education, 8*(6), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-020-00084-z>
- Grandeza, A. C., & Grandeza, R. A. (2024). A Unified Integration of Interactive Digital Platforms for Enhancing Performance and Assessment in Technology and Livelihood Education. *Nexus International Journal of Science and Education, 1*(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11331098>
- Guzeller, C. O. (2014). Relationship between ict variables and mathematics achievement based on pisa 2006 database: International evidence. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET, 13*(1), 184–192.
- Hu, X. (2018). The relationship between ict and student literacy in mathematics, reading, and science across 44 countries: A multilevel analysis. *Computers & Education, 125*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.05.021>
- Lee, Y. H. (2012). The effect of individual differences in the inner and outer states of ict on engagement in online reading activities and pisa 2009 reading literacy: Exploring the rela-

- relationship between the old and new reading literacy. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 22(3), 336–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2012.01.007>
- Schildkamp, K. (2019). Data teams in schools: Supporting data use for school improvement using a web-based tool. *Computers & Education*, 128, 383–398.
- Yadav, A., & Lundeberg, M. A. (2019). Simulations and stem learning: An integrative review. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 67(3), 531–551.